

ISCHEMIC HEART DISEASES. MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION

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Abstract: This article talks about myocardial infarction, which is one of the ischemic diseases of the heart. The article provides information on the types, origin, diagnosis and complications of myocardial infarction.

Key words: thrombus, necrosis, myocardium, infarct, atherosclerosis, hypertension, diabetes

Myocardial infarction is a myocardial infarction caused by blockage of the coronary arteries by thrombus or their compression

Necrosis (local death) of the heart muscle layer as a result of violation of the blood supply to the layer. With this disease

People aged 45-60 are affected. Men suffer from myocardial infarction more often than women, men aged 40-50

they get sick five times more. In recent years, the incidence of myocardial infarction is increasing. Myocardial infarction is especially common among people aged 45-60. Men suffer from myocardial infarction more often than women. Men aged 40-50 are sick five times more often. On average, women get sick 10-15 years later than men. There are also many people who have suffered myocardial infarction among the elderly people under 40 years old. Myocardial infarction is more common in patients with atherosclerosis, hypertension, and diabetes.

How does it come about?

Sometimes no triggering factors are needed for ischemic disease to turn into a heart attack: just waking up and getting up is enough. Stress or unusual physical activity increases the risk of heart attack.

How do you know if it's a heart attack?

The main symptom is severe pain in the chest, which is sometimes observed in the left arm and left shoulder. The pain is different: the chest is tight, hot. Along with pain, fear also covers, and a person loses peace.

There are other signs that differ depending on the type of infarction:

- As in the case of asthma, a person lacks air, the patient's condition does not improve from breath-relieving drugs;
- The person becomes weak, pale, hands and feet freeze;
- Arrhythmia develops;
- Stomach hurts, nausea is observed;
- A person loses balance, becomes weak, and symptoms of a stroke appear.

Doctors can determine if a heart attack has occurred or not with the help of an EKG.

Methods of treatment of myocardial infarction

Myocardial infarction may be suspected in a patient if:

- If a strong burning pain is felt behind the chest, it lasts more than 5-10 minutes;
- The pain does not subside with time, rest, or nitroglycerin;
- The pain is accompanied by severe weakness, nausea, vomiting, headache and dizziness.

If you suspect a myocardial infarction, immediately call an ambulance and start helping the patient. The earlier the first aid is given to the patient, the better the outcome. It is necessary to reduce the load on the heart, so the patient's head should be slightly raised. It is necessary to provide fresh air and try to calm the patient, it is possible to give sedatives. If there are drugs from the beta-blocker group, the patient should be given 1 tablet to chew (exactly for chewing, otherwise it will not work). If the patient has been taking these drugs regularly, then he will have to take an extra dose of the drug. To reduce the pain, it is necessary to give the patient an analgesic drug. If cardiac arrest is suspected (fainting, respiratory arrest, lack of pulse and unresponsiveness to external stimuli), resuscitation measures (artificial respiration and indirect heart massage) should be started immediately. If the patient is unconscious, the procedures should be continued until the doctors arrive.

Complications of myocardial infarction

— Complications of myocardial infarction always have a negative effect on the condition of the body. Of course, it depends on the area of damage to the myocardium. Heart rhythm disorders often develop in patients with myocardial infarction. Due to myocardial necrosis and scar formation, the contractility of the heart decreases and, as a result, heart failure develops.

As a result of extensive damage to the heart and the formation of large scars, a heart aneurysm can appear - a condition that threatens the patient's life and requires prompt treatment. "Aneurysm not only worsens the functioning of the heart, but also increases the probability of blood clot formation and the risk of its rupture," says the doctor.

Heart attacks are more common in people over 50 years old. Young men with a family history of heart attacks are also at risk.

In addition, smoking, alcohol consumption, high blood pressure, excess weight, poor diet and sedentary lifestyle also cause serious heart problems. If a person does not exercise enough, eventually any physical activity can make him redundant.

Genetics, age and gender cannot be argued with, and we choose our lifestyle. This can be a very boring recipe for prevention, but others don't work!

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